

APPLICATION OF THE EXPERIENCE OF DEVELOPED COUNTRIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

¹Muradova Maftuna Komilovna, ²Xolboyeva Bonu Gulmurodovna

¹TDPU in the name of Nizomi, Teacher of the "General Pedagogy" department

²Tashkent State Pedagogical University, Student of the Faculty of Natural Sciences

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10975137>

Abstract. *This article explores the use of effective practices in the educational system of developed countries. The study examines the experience of countries, studying modern approaches and how they can be successfully applied to the national education system. The study made practical recommendations to improve the quality of education, improve teaching methods and formulate public policy.*

Keywords: *educational reform, advanced experience, international practice, innovative approaches, quality of education.*

The education system plays an important role in the socio-economic development of any country. In the context of globalization, reforms and innovations in the field of education are important for the development of national systems. The experience of developed countries, their achievements in the field of education can serve to improve the education system of our country.

After Uzbekistan gained independence, reforming the education system and aligning it with international standards was set as a priority. In our country, special attention is paid to the field of education, and extensive reforms are being implemented in this regard. At the same time, it is an urgent issue to study the advanced experience of developed countries and introduce their effective practices into our national education system.

Important steps have been taken to improve the education system in Uzbekistan. In particular, special attention is being paid to issues such as strengthening the material and technical base of educational institutions, improving educational programs, and improving the qualifications of teachers. Also, a lot of work is being done on the wide implementation of information and communication technologies in the educational process [6].

However, based on today's requirements, there is a need to further improve our education system. For this, it is important to deeply study the best practices of developed countries and adapt their effective practices to our national education system.

The following methods were used in this study:

Content analysis - literature, legislative documents, state programs and other sources were thoroughly analyzed to study practices in the educational system of developed countries.

Comparative analysis - approaches to the education system of developed countries were compared and their advantages were evaluated.

Expert evaluation - interviews with experts in the field of education were conducted and their suggestions were taken into account [1].

It shows the need to use international experience to ensure sustainable development, improve the quality of education and ensure competitiveness. He emphasizes that the economic development of the country is closely related to the quality of the education system. It shows the importance of using modern information and communication technologies in the implementation of educational reforms.

According to the results of the research, the following experiences of developed countries can help to further improve the education system of our country:

The Finnish education system gives teachers a lot of freedom and places special emphasis on the development of children's individual abilities.

- Singapore has a strong emphasis on math and science and uses modern pedagogical technologies.
- A culture of teamwork and mutual support has been formed in Japanese schools.
- South Korea makes extensive use of online learning platforms and places special importance on digital literacy [2].

Studying the experience of developed countries shows that in order to improve the education system, it is necessary to pay attention to the following factors:

- Improving the qualifications of teachers and empowering them.
- Introduction of modern educational methods, increasing attention to science and technology.
- Taking into account the individual characteristics of children and applying a person-oriented approach.
- Use digital literacy and distance learning opportunities.
- Broad involvement of society in the educational process and formation of collective culture [3].

In the process of studying and analyzing the experience of developed countries, it is necessary to pay attention to the following important aspects:

Educational quality control system. In developed countries, the system of evaluation and control of the quality of education is well established. For example, in Finland, children's educational level is often assessed and monitored. In Singapore, national assessment programs have been introduced. It is important to apply these experiences in our country.

An environment of inter-school competition. In most developed countries, there is an atmosphere of healthy competition between schools. In the Netherlands, for example, schools are subject to student and parent choice. It is appropriate to introduce such an approach in our country.

Independence of educational institutions. It is known from the experience of developed countries that giving educational institutions wide powers and their independence increases the quality of education. In Singapore and Finland, schools are free to develop their own curricula and organize pedagogical processes.

Involving parents in the educational process. In advanced countries, parents are actively involved in the educational process. For example, in South Korea, parents are actively involved in school life and pay great attention to their children's education. This experience should be used in our country as well.

Training of qualified teachers. In developed countries, special attention is paid to the teaching profession. In Finland and Singapore, the process of selecting and training teachers is highly organized. By applying this experience, it is possible to improve the qualifications of teachers in our country [5].

In short, the experience of developed countries helps to improve the education system of our country. To apply these experiments in practice, it is necessary to do the following:

- It is necessary to give wide powers to educational institutions and increase their independence. Schools should be empowered to develop their own programs and freely organize pedagogical processes.

- It is necessary to fundamentally improve the system of selection and training of teachers. It is important to improve the reputation of the teaching profession and attract qualified personnel.

- It is necessary to introduce a system of monitoring and evaluating the quality of education. National assessment programs should be developed and children's learning levels should be regularly assessed.

- It is necessary to create an atmosphere of healthy competition between schools. For this purpose, it is appropriate to introduce a mechanism for referring schools to students based on selection.

- It is important to expand the use of information and communication technologies and introduce distance education opportunities.

- Practical mechanisms should be developed to involve parents and society in the educational process [5].

In the course of these researches, the best experiences in the educational system of developed countries were deeply studied and analyzed. The obtained results served to determine ways to improve the education system of our country. Practical ways of introducing these experiences into our national education system were also considered.

REFERENCES

1. Barber, M., & Mourshed, M. (2007). "How the world's best-performing school systems come out on top". McKinsey & Company.
2. Hanushek, E. A., & Woessmann, L. (2010). "The high cost of low educational performance: The long-run economic impact of improving PISA outcomes". OECD Publishing.
3. OECD (2018). "The Future of Education and Skills: Education 2030". OECD Publishing, Paris.
4. Sahlberg, P. (2011). "Finnish Lessons: What Can the World Learn from Educational Change in Finland?". Teachers College Press.
5. Schleicher, A. (2018). "World Class: How to Build a 21st-Century School System". OECD Publishing.
6. UNESCO (2021). "Reimagining our futures together: A new social contract for education". UNESCO Publishing.